

QUANTIFICATION OF SOURCES OF VARIABILITY IN CFRP PLATES CURED IN AUTOCLAVE

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1. Introduction

Variability in composite materials is directly related to both manufacturing process and raw materials. At each stage of manufacturing, new variables are introduced increasing the variability of the system. The effects of these variabilities depend on the scale which they are studied. For the structural analysis, the system response is assessed by acknowledging the dispersion in the materials properties [1]. However, a majority of the analyses are based on deterministic models which use elevated safety factors. As consequence, an increase in the weight of the structure is observed, thus negating the elevated strength to weight ratios anticipated for these materials.

The research works that deal with variability in composites are oriented towards the characterization of the dispersion in the mechanical properties [2]. The data recollected are then used in stochastic models to predict the structural behaviour and to optimize the design. For the composite structure manufacturing, the works are oriented towards the reduction of uncertainties [3]. Nevertheless, a number of sources of variability cannot be reduced given that some of them depend on a previous manufacturing stage (e.g. the quality of the prepregs) or on restrictions in the actual fabrication process (e.g. complex geometries or budgetary constraints) [4]. Also, it is acknowledged that there is a shortage of real data for certain sources of variability; one of them is the ply misalignment.

As recognized in literature, the sources of variability are strongly linked to the manufacturing of the composite. Thus, their identification and quantification must be performed on the actual fabrication process. In this study, a set of certain

parameters are studied during the cure in autoclave of unidirectional (UD) prepregs of a carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP). The sources of variability controlled are the following:

- Variation in the mass per unit area (areal weight) of the prepregs.
- Misalignment of plies during the manual lay-up process.
- Effects of different vacuum bagging configuration in the CFRP plate.
- The thickness in the total and individual ply of the cured plate.

After the quantification of the aforementioned parameters, a database of the composite material is build in order to regroup all the sources of variability acquired during the CFRP plates manufacturing. Subsequently, this database will be used to provide the input parameters of a finite element analysis (FEA) model which will take into account the variabilities measured.

2. Measurement of variability sources

2.1 Materials

In the course of this work, 12 CFRP plates have been manufactured. The plates have dimensions of 615 x 300 mm and are made form a Hexcel Composites high strength carbon (CHS)/epoxy UD prepreg system, M10.1/38%/UD300/CHS. The plates have a 16 plies $[90/-45/0/(+45)_2/0/-45/90]_s$ quasi-istropic stratification. For the manufacturing of the CFRP plates, 2 different lots of the prepreg have been used, R1 and R2. The plates are produced in 3 autoclave batches identified chronologically as A, B and C. 3 plates are produced in each autoclave batch A and B using the R1 material. For the batch C, 6 plates are made using R2.

In these experiments, the prepreg cutting and lay-up are both manual operations. The plates are placed onto a mould and prepared for the curing in autoclave. The vacuum bagging configuration used can indeed modify the properties of the cured plate. In batch A, the bagging was configured according to our experience with the UD prepreg M21/T700CG. This material is a quasi net preimpregnate system. This configuration uses a single layer of bleeding fabric and a perforated film between the plate and the breathing cloth. Since the resin M10.1 has a lower viscosity than that of the M21 (0.4 Pa.s in comparison to 1.0 Pa.s for the later) and a higher matrix content by weight (38% to 34 % of the M21), the single layer of bleeding fabric was not sufficient to contain the resin excess. Hence, the additional resin passed onto the breathing cloth. This cloth is essential to maintain a uniform application of the vacuum in all the composite parts. Therefore, the vacuum bagging configuration in batch B employed a double layer of bleeding material and the perforated separator film was changed to a microperforated one. This configuration has effectively blocked the additional resin flow from passing towards the breathing cloth. This configuration is also used for the batch C. The differences in the vacuum bagging configuration are represented in Table 1.

2.2 Measurement methods

During the manufacturing of the CFRP plates, a protocol for an orderly measurement of certain sources of variability is established. The first property identified is the mass per unit area of the UD prepreg. This property is an early indicator of the dispersion in the fibre and matrix volume fractions. For its determination, two methods are employed. The first method is the control of all of the prepreg plies before being laid-up into the composite plate. The implementation of this method as a systematic measurement is proven difficult due to the added uncertainties from material handling. Therefore, a second method is put in place in order to measure specimens randomly taken from the prepreg roll. The results show little difference in the mean and standard deviation of the areal weight between the first and the second method. The second method is preferred for the global control of the

variability in the mass per unit area of the composite prepreg.

The second source of variability identified is the misalignment of the plies associated to the manual lay-up of the UD prepreg. In order to measure this misalignment, a digital camera is placed 2m above the work zone, and is used to take images of the lay-up sequence (cf. Figure 1). A calibration grid is used to correct the image distortion of the camera lens. Even though that the misalignments are issued from several factors, they are more likely to depend on the operator. This experiment permits the measurement of the actual misalignment in order to use real values associated to this property. Also, this method allows the identification of local defects and gaps in the prepregs due to ply coalition.

After the lay-up, the plates are placed into the autoclave for a typical cure cycle. The M10.1 is a resin that cures at 120 °C. The heating and cooling rates are maintained at 2 °C min⁻¹. After the material polymerisation, the overall thickness of the CFRP plates is controlled by means of a coordinate-measuring machine (CMM). Then, four plates coming from batches A and B are used to form 2 technological evaluators each. The evaluators, which their dimensions are: width = 130 mm and length = 600 mm, are employed in a composite repair testing campaign [5]. After the tests, one evaluator coming from each autoclave batch is used to obtain 4 specimens having dimensions of 20 mm by 130 mm. A series of photographs of the cross section of the specimens are taken and then the images are post processed to measure the actual ply thicknesses of the composite plate.

3. Results

3.1 Mass per unit area

During the fabrication of CFRP plates in batches A and B, all prepreg plies have been controlled by means of method 1, described in section 2.2, to obtain its mass per unit area (samples A and B). The prepreg plies used in the composite repair tests have been also measured by this method (sample DR). The areal weight for this material lot is 501.5 g m⁻² with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 1.6 %. The dispersion in this property is found to be in the

expected interval, slightly higher than that of an aeronautical material (i.e. a CV of 1% [6]). Then, a new sample of 35 specimens is controlled using method 2 (sample R1), under the norm ISO 10352. The specimens are randomly taken from the prepreg roll. The results employing this method are in good accordance with samples of A, B and DR samples taken with method 1, which observe an areal weight of 500.7 g m^{-2} and a CV of 1.1 %. The Figure 2 shows the mean of the mass per unit area for each sample while the error bars show the confidence interval for the mean using a “t distribution” with a probability of 95%.

For the lot R2, which is used to fabricate the plates of batch C, a sample of 10 elements is taken from random locations of the prepreg roll. This lot has an areal weight of 478.1 g m^{-2} with a CV of 2.25 %.

A direct comparison of R1 and R2 shows evidence of statistical difference in the mean between the two samples (cf. Figure 3); meanwhile, their variances do not show a statistical difference. Even though that the controlled material have similar dispersion in their values of mass per unit area (approximately 2 %), the difference between their mean values can lead to uncertainties in the manufacturing of composite structures that use two or more batches of raw materials.

Finally the values obtained for the mass per unit area were verified by weighting the composite plates before the curing cycle. A difference between the actual plate weight and its calculated value is less than 2 % (cf. Table 2).

3.2 Ply misalignment

The lay-up of the prepreg plies is made manually, thus some uncertainties are generated while placing the plies to form the composite plate. Indeed, this operation is quite dependent on factors related to the operator, such as skill and fatigue. The ply orientation is measured in the images taken during the lay-up stage. The plates had to be removed from the work zone to be vacuum debulked after the collation of the first 8 plies and then replaced onto the grid to continue the lay-up of the last 8 plies. In order to have the same reference within a single plate, all measures are referenced to the 1st ply at 90°

(base ply). Figure 4 shows the ply misalignment for all plates. The measured misalignments are randomly distributed, with a range of values from -1° to $+1.5^\circ$. The overall positive rotation bias (cf. Figure 5) is explained by the fact that all the plies were laid-up using the same technique and same operators.

3.3 Effects of Vacuum Bagging configuration

After the polymerisation of the plates in batch A, the breathing material is impregnated with the exceeding resin. The resin lost by the plate is 12 to 15 % of the uncured plate weight. After changing the vacuum bagging configuration (cf. Table 1) in batch B, the exceeding resin flow is 6 %. For the plates in batch C, which also uses this configuration, the exceeding resin is 5 %. The difference between B and C plates, which have been produced using the same vacuum bagging configuration, can be explained by the use of different materials in each batch (R1 for B and R2 for C). Further testing is necessary to confirm this hypothesis.

Varying the vacuum bagging configuration has indeed an impact on the cured material properties. It is shown that the excess in the resin flow in batch A compared to batch B reduced the overall thickness of the cured plate. After measuring the 6 plates in a CMM, the mean thickness is 4.7 mm for the plates of batch A mm and 5.1 mm for those manufactured in batch B (cf. Table 2). The M10.1/CHS has a nominal cured ply thickness of 0.320 mm. The difference between the overall thicknesses in both batches is greater than the thickness of a nominal ply. Hence, this can create conflicts during the dimensioning of a composite structure. In addition, the mapping of the plate shows that the thickness is not constant along and across the plate. The thickness has a maximal value around the centre of the plate, meanwhile the minimum value is found at the corners (cf. Figures 6a and 6b).

3.4 Thickness of the cured plates and plies

In order to measure the actual thicknesses of the cured ply, 4 specimens from batches A and B are cut. The plies thicknesses are measured from micrographs taken from 6 zones along the cross section of each specimen (cf. Figure 7). 2 zones are

measured per micrograph. Due to the chosen stacking sequence, the plies 4/5, 8/9 and 12/13 are difficult to distinguish separately. Hence, these pairs of plies are treated separately as “double plies”.

The specimens from plate A2 (cf. Figure 8a) have a lower mean thickness than those from plate B2 (cf. Figure 8b). The distribution of the ply thicknesses along the cross is similar for both plates. This is an indication that the flow of exceeding resin is similar across the plate, due the thicknesses of the plies do not show any clear tendency to increase or reduce their values towards the top or the bottom of the plate. As indicated by the confidence intervals for the mean value of the thickness, the variability of ply thicknesses the batch A (CV of 14 %) is greater than that of the batch B (CV 9%).

Finally, by observing the cross section of the specimen is evident that there is a variation in the thicknesses of the plies along the composite core. As well, by comparing the dispersion of ply thickness to the dispersion of the main plate in the single ply this variation is found in the order of 14 % for the plates in the batch A and 9% for the plies of batch B (cf. Figure 9). However, the CV of the overall plate thickness is approximately 2 % for both plates. The difference between the thickness of the ply and the plate comes from a geometric coupling in the plies; e.g., for any given reduction in the thickness of the ply, at the zone of the adjacent ply there is an augmentation of its thickness (cf. Figure 10). This effect has an impact in the local volume fractions and on the relative position of the ply in the cross section, thus changing the stiffness of the CFRP, in particular during flexion.

4. Numerical implementation of local variabilities in composite structural analysis.

After the collection of certain sources of variability, they can be used as input parameters of a FEA model. This model will take into account the local variabilities to assess the final structural properties. The approach needs a data pre-treatment of the acquired values during the systematic measurements. By using programming tools, a database is generated by employing homogenization methods to determine the local material properties.

As an example of application; the database supplies the input parameters into a FEA model, in which the material properties vary locally in each mesh (cf. Figure 11a). Then, the numerical analysis is run to find a failure criterion (cf. Figure 11b). This analysis is then performed several times in order to vary randomly the properties of the material in each mesh by using the Monte Carlo Method [7]. The main goal of this approach is to find the probability density function (PDF) of the studied parameter (cf. Figure 11c).

5. Conclusions

In order to study some of the sources of variability in CRFP structures, a measurement protocol is established. This protocol allows a systematically characterization of several variables during the manufacturing of composite plates. The studied parameters are:

- Mass per unit area of the UD prepreg.
- The ply misalignment during the manual lay-up.
- The effects of the exceeding resin flow during curing.
- Variation in the cured thickness of the plates and plies as well as undulation effects in those plies.

The recompilation of all the data will permit to create a FEA model closer to reality, as this model will take into account the different local variabilities to find a global behaviour of the composite structure.

However, several parameters are yet to be characterized, especially at local level. The first parameter to be correlated is the volume fraction of the fibre and matrix of the level of the plate (global) and at the level of the ply (local). Then the measurements of the ply orientation must be refined to include local misalignments. This measure could be refined towards the determination (and correlation) of the cured fibre orientation at ply level.

In conclusion, a perspective of the variability of a composite structure is presented. As remarked, this is a broad problem due to the multiple factors that are implied at each scale in the composite material. The global behaviour of a composite structure is the assembly of infinity local variabilities, which in conjunction, create the material properties. This

variabilities depend, not only from the manufacturing but also on the raw materials, design constrains and expertise. It's clear that a big number of variables need to be characterized in order to obtain the realistic dispersion in values to input the stochastic models.

(a)

(b)

Fig.1. Composite UD prepreg during the lay-up phase (a) plate C22 and the calibration grid (b) detail of a ply collation

Fig.2. Mean of the mass per unit area using the method 1 (Samples A, B and DR) and method 2 (sample R1).

Fig.3. Comparison of the mass per unit area between the 2 prepregs lots: R1 and R2.

Fig.4. Difference between the real ply angle and the theoretical stratification for all 6 plates of batch C.

- - -> Base ply reference
 - - -> Actual orientation of ply No. 9 [90°]

Fig.5. Example of the misalignment between the base ply (reference) and a given ply.

Fig.7. Cross section of the laminated plate B2(2).

Fig.6. Mean ply thickness of the plates fabricated in two different batches (a) plate A2 and (b) plate B2.

(a)

(b)

Fig.8. Distribution of the mean ply thickness for (a) plate A2 and (b) plate B2.

Fig.9. CV of the overall thickness arranged by single plies, double plies and the plate in each plate.

Fig.10. Reconstruction of the cross section of the plate A2(1) from the actual measures.

(a)

Material properties locally variable

(b)

Numeric testing:

« Tsai Criterion »
« Strain Field »
...

(c) Probability Density Function of the computed structural properties

Fig.11. Numerical analysis proposed (a) structure discretisation giving each mesh its own properties (b) numerical testing and (b) PDF obtained after several tests.

Batch A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single layer of bleeding fabric • Perforated film between the bleeding and the breathing layers. • Entouring the plates with mosite
Batch B/C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two layers of bleeding fabric • Microperforated film between the bleeding and breathing cloths. • Without mosite

Tab.1. Configuration of the vacuum bagging of the different autoclave batches.

Plate (lot)	Plates weight [g]	Resin lost [g]	Ratio	Plate thick. [mm]
A1 (R1)	1477,7	-187,6	-12,7 %	4,7
A2 (R1)	1476,1	-191,8	-13,0 %	4,7
A3 (R1)	1477,6	-216,3	-14,6 %	4,6
B1 (R1)	1483,2	-90,9	-6,1 %	5,1
B2 (R1)	1483,2	-90,8	-6,1 %	5,1
B3 (R1)	1485,1	-96,4	-6,5 %	5,1
C11 (R2)	1415,1	-67,8	-4,8 %	
C12 (R2)	1419,3	-58,2	-4,1 %	
C13 (R2)	1414,3	-65,0	-4,6 %	
C21 (R2)	1415,4	-68,0	-4,8 %	
C22 (R2)	1414,9	-67,6	-4,8 %	
C23 (R2)	1418,9	-77,2	-5,4 %	

Tab.2. Weight of the plates before the curing cycle, resin lost during the cycle and mean plate thickness after polymerisation.

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